

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

AN INQUIRY INTO THE APPLICATION OF CALCULUS TO PHYSICS

Yang Xiuchuan

lecturer at School of Mathematics and statistics,
JiNing Normal University,
Ulanqab, Inner Mongolia, P. R. China

Abstract

Calculus, as an important mathematical tool for analysing physical problems, can not only help us grasp the essential laws of physical phenomena more efficiently and deeply, but also significantly improve the ability of quantitative analysis of problems, which is of great theoretical value and practical significance for physics research and learning. This paper mainly introduces some applications of calculus in physics, according to the specific background of the problem, the application of the relevant laws of physics, the problem is reduced to the calculation of calculus.

Keywords: calculus; kinematics; mechanics; electromagnetism; quantum mechanics.

Calculus, as an important branch of mathematics, has wide and deep applications in physics. From describing the motion of objects to studying electromagnetic phenomena, from analysing mechanical systems to exploring the quantum world, calculus plays a key role. It provides physicists with a powerful tool for accurately describing natural phenomena, building physical models and performing quantitative analyses.

1 Applications of Calculus to Kinesiology

1.1 Displacement, velocity and acceleration

Displacement is the change in position of an object, velocity is the rate of change of displacement versus time, and acceleration is the rate of change of velocity versus time. Using calculus, we can accurately describe the position, velocity, and acceleration of an object at different moments in time. For example, if the acceleration function $a(t)$ of an object is known, the velocity function $v(t) = \int a(t)dt + v_0$ (where v_0 is the initial velocity) can be obtained by integration, and the displacement function $s(t) = \int v(t)dt + s_0$ (where s_0 is the initial displacement) can be obtained by integration. Conversely, if the displacement function is known, the velocity and acceleration functions can be obtained by differentiation. This relationship is very important in the study of various forms of motion such as linear and curvilinear motion of objects.

1.2 Parabolic motion

For parabolic motion, we can use calculus to analyse the trajectory of an object. The motion of the object is decomposed into horizontal and vertical directions, with constant velocity in the horizontal direction and acceleration by gravity in the vertical direction. By applying the kinematics formulas to the horizontal and vertical directions respectively, and integrating and deriving them using calculus, the position and velocity of an object at any moment can be obtained, thus accurately describing the trajectory of a paraboloid. Parabolic motion can be regarded as the combined motion of uniform linear motion in the horizontal direction and

uniformly variable linear motion in the vertical direction. Calculus is useful in analysing physical quantities such as velocity and displacement in parabolic motion.

(1) Speed analysis

Suppose an object is thrown with an initial velocity v_0 and an angle θ with the horizontal. Decompose the initial velocity into the horizontal direction $v_{0x} = v_0 \cos\theta$ and the vertical direction $v_{0y} = v_0 \sin\theta$. In the horizontal direction, the velocity v_0 is constant because there is no acceleration in the horizontal direction, i.e., $v_x(t) = v_0 \cos\theta$. In the vertical direction, the acceleration $a = -g$ (g is the acceleration due to gravity), and the integration of the acceleration by the derivative $a = \frac{dv_y}{dt}$ of velocity

with respect to time yields $v_y(t) = v_{0y} + \int_0^t a dt$, which is $v_y(t) = v_0 \sin\theta - gt$.

(2) Displacement analysis

For a horizontal displacement x , since v_x is a constant, integrating over it gives $x(t) = \int_0^t v_x dt$ by the fact that velocity is the derivative of displacement with respect to time $v_x = \frac{dx}{dt}$, so $x(t) = v_0 \cos\theta \cdot t$

.For the vertical displacement y , $v_y = \frac{dy}{dt}$, integrate over $v_y(t)$ to find y , $y(t) = \int_0^t v_y(t) dt$, i.e., $y(t) = v_0 \sin\theta \cdot t - \frac{1}{2} gt^2$.

2 Applications of Calculus to Mechanics

2.1 Newton's second law

Newton's second law $F = ma$, where F is the force, m is the mass of the object, and a is the acceleration. Using calculus, we can apply Newton's second law to more complex mechanical problems. For example, when a force is a function of time, position, or velocity, the velocity and displacement of an object as a function of time can be obtained by integrating or deriving the acceleration. For the motion of an object under a variable force, calculus can help us solve the equations of motion of the object to accurately describe the object's state of motion.

2.2 Work and energy

Work is the accumulation of force over displacement and is defined as $W = \int F \cdot ds$, where F is the force and ds is the differential element of displacement. The work done by an object under different forces can be calculated by integration. Energy includes kinetic energy, potential energy, etc. Kinetic energy $E_k = \frac{1}{2}mv^2$, the rate of change of kinetic energy with time, i.e. power, can be obtained by deriving the velocity. Potential energy is related to position, and the corresponding force can be obtained by deriving the potential energy function. Using the law of conservation of energy, i.e., the total energy of a system remains constant, calculus can be used to solve various problems in mechanical systems, such as collisions of objects, vibrations of springs, etc.

3 Applications of Calculus to Electromagnetism

3.1 Electric and magnetic fields

The electric and magnetic field strengths can be obtained by integrating the charge and current distributions. For example, for an electric field generated by a point charge, according to Coulomb's law, the electric field strength $\vec{E} = \frac{kq}{r^2} \hat{r}$, where k is the Coulomb constant, q is the electric quantity of the point charge, r is the distance, and \hat{r} is the unit vector. The electric field generated by an arbitrary charge distribution can be obtained by integrating the electric field of multiple point charges. Similarly, the strength of a magnetic field can be obtained by integrating over a current distribution. Using calculus, we can analyse the properties of electric and magnetic fields, such as the divergence of the electric field and the curl of the magnetic field, to gain a deeper understanding of electromagnetic phenomena.

3.2 Electromagnetic induction

The phenomenon of electromagnetic induction means that a changing magnetic field produces an electric field and a changing electric field produces a magnetic field. According to Faraday's law of electromagnetic induction, the induced electromotive force is

$\varepsilon = -\frac{d\Phi}{dt}$, where Φ is the magnetic flux. The mag-

nitude of the induced electromotive force can be obtained by taking the derivative of the magnetic flux. In AC circuits, the properties of inductance and capacitance can also be described by calculus. For example, the relationship between voltage and current for the in-

ductance is $V_L = L \frac{dI}{dt}$ and the relationship between

current and voltage for the capacitance is $I_C = C \frac{dV}{dt}$

, where L is the inductance and C is the capacitance.

4 Applications of Calculus to Quantum Mechanics

4.1 Wave function

In quantum mechanics, the states of microscopic particles are described by wave functions. The wave function satisfies the Schrödinger equation, which is a partial differential equation that needs to be solved using calculus. By solving Schrödinger's equation, the probability distribution of information such as the energy, position, and momentum of a particle can be obtained. The application of calculus in quantum mechanics helps us to understand strange phenomena in the microscopic world, such as quantum entanglement and tunneling effects.

4.2 Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle

Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle is one of the fundamental principles of quantum mechanics, which is important for our understanding of the nature of the microscopic world and the fundamental concepts of quantum mechanics. Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle shows that the position and momentum of a particle cannot be determined exactly at the same time, and that

their uncertainties satisfy $\Delta x \Delta p \geq \frac{h}{2}$, where h is the

reduced Planck constant. This principle can be obtained by performing calculus on the wave function.

Calculus is used in physics across the spectrum from classical mechanics to modern physics. It provides physicists with powerful analytical tools that enable them to accurately describe natural phenomena, build physical models, and perform quantitative analyses. As physics continues to develop, the applications of calculus will continue to expand and deepen, revealing more of the mysteries of nature.

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